

SOME ISSUES OF ENSURING PUBLIC SAFETY IN THE CONTEXT OF ADVANCED WORLD EXPERIENCE

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The completely new mechanisms and procedures for organizing work in the direction of public safety on the basis of the principle of “Serving the interests of the people” are introduced, and mutual purposeful cooperation of state bodies with public structures is established.

It is known that ensuring public order and safety is recognized as one of the main functions of the state. In order to implement this function, various organizational and legal mechanisms are developed and implemented. In particular, the fact that thousands of political, cultural and sports mass events are held every year in our republic is a proof of the rule of peace and tranquility in our country.

Public safety is a state of protection of the vital interests of the individual, society and the state from the consequences of criminal and other illegal actions, social conflicts, natural disasters, earthquakes, epidemics, epizootics, man-made disasters, accidents and fires. Although legal documents usually use the terms “maintenance” (protection) in relation to public order and “ensure” in relation to public safety, the content of these types of law enforcement activities are mostly consistent.

The concept of public safety is defined as a state of protection of the vital interests of the individual, society and the state as a result of other illegal actions and social conflicts, natural disasters, epidemics, epizootics, accidents, and extraordinary situations caused by fire.

Maintaining public order includes the concepts of ensuring personal safety of citizens and public safety at the same time. However, although the concepts of “personal security of citizens” and “public security” are related to the concept of “public order”, they differ from each other.

Despite the widespread use of these concepts in the legislation of our country and within legal science, a unified approach to their definition has not yet been developed in the legal literature¹. Such an approach requires revealing the essence of concepts such as “public event”, “public order”, “public safety” and forming their theoretical definitions.

It shows that there is no single opinion and unanimity regarding the concept of maintaining public order and safety. In particular, the French scientist George Wedel put forward the opinion that “Safety is an activity aimed at preventing dangers that threaten the community or certain individuals, and it includes threats to state security and the prevention of simple accidents”².

¹Ismailov I., Ziyodullaev M.Z. Administrative activities of internal affairs bodies: Textbook. - T., 2014. - 425 p.; Ismailov I., Muhamadaliev D.S. and others. Management of activities of internal affairs agencies to maintain public order and ensure public safety: Course of lectures - T., 2013. P.322.

²Wedel J. Administrative law of France. Translation from French - M., 1993. - P. 132.

To elucidate the issue, it can be concluded that public order and public safety are different types of social relations, and there is a close connection between them: each of these group relations is a condition for the existence of the other. In addition, the content of public order and public security corresponds to the area where relevant social relations ensure respect for the dignity and worth of the individual, which are vital interests of the individual and society, and respect for the peace of the society and the individual.

In our opinion, public safety is a state of protection of the vital interests of the individual, society and the state from the consequences of criminal and other illegal activities, social conflicts, natural disasters, earthquakes, epidemics, epizootics, major disasters, accidents and fires. Therefore, it is important to consider it from different perspectives, including the definition of the object of control and the methods of influence.

Today, the changes taking place in the political and social life of our country, especially the tasks related to the security and stability of our country, require a very serious approach, in which systematic, clear and legal division of the actions of the internal affairs bodies and their regular improvement is one of the issues awaiting its solution.

Over the past period, extensive work was carried out to improve the system of internal affairs bodies. In particular, significant work was done on the development and strengthening of the lower level of the internal affairs bodies, which was established to maintain public order in the neighborhoods, ensure the safety of citizens, prevent offenses and fight against crime.

In fact, the internal affairs bodies ensure the existence of peace and stability in the country, the rights and freedoms of citizens of independent Uzbekistan. A number of Decrees were adopted as a logical continuation of the ongoing reforms in the system of internal affairs bodies in order to more firmly guarantee the provision of life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inviolable rights of a person recognized as the highest value in Uzbekistan. For instance, Resolution

No. PR-6196 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated on March 26, 2021 "On measures to raise the quality of the activities of internal affairs bodies to a new level in the field of ensuring public safety and fighting crime"³, Decree No. PD-5050 "On additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of ensuring public safety and fighting crime" on April 2, 2021⁴, Decree No. PD-5076 "On measures to introduce a qualitatively new system of training professional personnel for internal affairs bodies"⁵ on April 15, 2021 are primarily examples.

These normative-legal documents adopted by the head of state define a number of tasks, such as improving the activities of internal affairs bodies, regulating them, preventing crimes, ensuring public safety and fighting crime.

Respectively, the work of the internal affairs bodies in the fight against crime, prevention of violations, maintaining public order and ensuring the safety of citizens, and increasing the legal awareness of the population has also improved. The most important thing

³Resolution No. PR-6196 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated on March 26, 2021 "On measures to raise the quality of the activities of internal affairs bodies to a new level in the field of ensuring public safety and fighting crime" // lex.uz.

⁴Decree No. PD-5050 "On additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of ensuring public safety and fighting crime" on April 2, 2021// lex.uz.

⁵Decree No. PD-5076 "On measures to introduce a qualitatively new system of training professional personnel for internal affairs bodies" on April 15, 2021 // lex.uz.

is that the cooperation of the system employees with the people has been strengthened. Establishing stability, peace and tranquility in society, ensuring unconditional observance of human rights and freedoms is an important condition for achieving the goals set by the large-scale reforms that are being implemented to further develop the country from a socio-economic point of view, increase the well-being of the population, and build a legal democratic state.

As a result of the reforms that have been implemented over the past years to improve the activities of the internal affairs bodies, including its focus on maintaining public order and ensuring safety, first of all, the activities of all the sectoral services of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their local sub-structures have been improved based on the requirements of the time, their organizational structure and main tasks were clearly defined. In addition, the activities of the internal affairs bodies, in particular, its patrol-post service units, in order to maintain public order and security during public events, have been improved, and the responsibility of the employees serving in them has been increased. Along with all the sectoral services of internal affairs bodies, the system of patrol post and public order maintenance service, which is directly involved in the maintenance of public order and security, has been improved.

The material and technical base of field services, structural structures and military units, whose main task in the system of internal affairs bodies is to maintain public order and ensure safety, was improved, they were provided with modern motor vehicles, computers and communication tools, service weapons, and finally, the activities of internal affairs bodies, in particular, its activity in maintaining public order and ensuring its safety is being legally strengthened⁶.

It is extremely necessary to determine the rights and obligations of all participants involved in public events. When conducting a public event, the rights of the internal affairs bodies to surround the areas adjacent to the object of the public event, and to control the compliance of the audience with the rules of the event, are defined. The tasks of the National Guard units are to assist the units of the internal affairs bodies in ensuring the public safety of the facility during public events.

It is necessary to collect information about possible terrorist threats in the object of the public event or in the nearby area of the state security service and take measures to eliminate them by exchanging information with other law enforcement agencies. The Ministry of Emergencies should determine the factors of danger and threats that can cause fire in time, and ensure their prevention and early prevention of their occurrence. During public events, the Ministry of Health should provide emergency medical and first aid to the victims. In our views, it is appropriate to introduce changes and additions to the legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to ensure public order and security during the above-mentioned events.

It can be concluded that, the analysis of the above-mentioned problems confirms, it is necessary to develop and adopt the draft law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On public events" and make changes to a number of laws related to ensuring public safety during other public events by now.

⁶Decree PD-2883 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated on April 12, 2017 "On organizational measures to further improve the activities of internal affairs bodies" // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. Art. 247.

To sum up the issue, maintaining public order and ensuring the safety of citizens is one of the important issues in all countries, and the management of the structural units engaged in this task is carried out through various ways and methods. Each country has its own experience in this field, and their study and implementation in the system of ensuring public order and security in our country is one of the urgent issues today. Because, as the President of the country Sh.M.Mirziyoev noted, “in order to increase the effectiveness of internal affairs bodies, we should pay special attention to the task of wide application of new working methods and mechanisms, in particular, digital technologies, to practical activities, having studied the advanced experience of developed foreign countries in depth”.